

Short name	Voluntary carbon market standards	Long name	Ongoing VCS methodology development
Geographical scope	Global		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Carbon capture and storage (CCS) is an important mitigation solution, but there has not been a comprehensive set of methodologies available for various CCS projects to access voluntary carbon markets and generate carbon revenue. However, an industry consortium called CCS+ is currently developing a methodological framework with robust requirements for monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) and additionality. Public consultations on these new methodologies are ongoing and can be accessed at https://verra.org/consultations/. In 2023, methodologies for a full range of CCS projects, including those that reduce emissions and those that involve carbon capture and utilization (CCU) and carbon removals, will become available through Verra's Voluntary Carbon Standard (VCS).</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of the fundamental MRV requirements involved in carbon market methodologies among carbon market stakeholders is low • Consequent adoption of high-quality and consistent methodologies is important for environmental integrity and credibility. • CCS is seen by some NGOs and publics as risky, consistent messaging on MRV requirements is key to build trust 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRV Readiness • MRV methodologies 		
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCS+ Initiative (2023): CCS+ Initiative 		